

ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND VOCATIONAL EDUCATION: A PANACEA FOR UN-EMPLOYABILITY OF NIGERIAN GRADUATES.

BY

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria, a developing country with huge resources (both human and material) at her disposal yet she has been ranked among the poorest nations in the world largely due to human factors. This has led to social problems such as poverty, mass unemployment, crimes of various degrees, illiteracy, inadequate health care system, political instability etc. This paper is of the opinion that training students sufficiently in entrepreneurship and vocational education can lead to unemployment reduction and self-reliance in the country because they offer many opportunities for the recipients of this education for self-employment and employment of others. Indeed, with adequate training in entrepreneurship and vocational education, a trainee can always transfer skills to related vocational areas in a gainful manner. It is against this background that this paper examines the concepts of entrepreneurship and vocational education and how this type of education can lead to self-reliance. The paper concludes and recommends that the government should take pragmatic steps towards incorporating entrepreneurship education in the curriculum of vocational and technical education at all levels of education in the country.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship education, vocational education, unemployability.

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship and vocational education is the kind of education that helps in solving national economic problems by absorbing graduates and thus overcoming the problems of poverty and unemployment in the society. This type of education is aimed at equipping individuals with skills, competence, knowledge and attitudes that are required for absorption in the labour market thereby making them self-reliant.

The world over, entrepreneurship and vocational education is gaining a lot of popularity and publicity but unfortunately this widely desired education is yet to catch up fully with Nigerian education planners, educators, students and highly interested individuals that would have embraced it for self-employment (Okomanyi, 2008). One of the national objectives of development as articulated in the national policy on Education of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004) revised is self-reliance and the government at all levels in recognition of the important role of self-reliance and self-employment in reducing poverty, unemployment and other social vices in the country introduced some programmes of assistance such as Operation Feed the Nation (OFN), Green Revolution, War Against Indiscipline (WAI), Directorate of Food, Road and Rural Infrastructure (DFRRI), National Directorate of Employment (NDE), Better life for Rural Women, Peoples' Bank of Nigeria, Community Banks, Oil Mineral Producing Areas Development Commission, Vision 2010, Family Economic Advancement Programme, Poverty Alleviation programme, National Eradication Programme etc.

These attempts by the government were to reduce poverty and unemployment and to encourage self-employment and self-reliance in the country but then the question is, to what extent have these programmes solved the problems of unemployment in Nigeria?

According to Shaban (2001) in Adamu (2006), the programmes put in place only succeeded in creating and consolidating a poverty industry whose beneficiaries have been the initiators, their wives, close allies and agents. While the leaders of these programmes had a field day with funds, the larger population of Nigerian sank deeper and deeper into the ocean of poverty.

It is in response to these problems that entrepreneurship and vocational education have become very important to tackle this hydra-headed monster called "poverty" which requires a multi-pronged approach by all and sundry.

CONCEPTUALIZING ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND VOCATIONAL EDUCATION

a) *Entrepreneurship Education*

Paul (2005) defines entrepreneurship education as a specialized training given to students of vocational and technical education to acquire the skills, ideas and managerial abilities and capabilities for self-employment rather than being employed for pay.

Akintola (2001) in Osuala (2002) quoted U.S. Colorado educators as defining entrepreneurship education as "a programme or part of the programme that prepares individuals to undertake formation and or operation of small scale business which include franchise operations for the purpose of performing all business relating to a product or service, with emphasis given to the social responsibilities, legal requirements and risk for the sake of profit involved in the conduct of a private business". It is in the light of the above definitions that the writer considers that the knowledge of entrepreneurship education can have tremendous impact on the individual as well as the economy of the nation as a whole.

According to Solomon Alabulyader and Ramam (2019) entrepreneurship education has taken a sharp shift from typical classroom lecture collection strategy to modern strategy that lay more effort on nurturing competences, improving expertise, abilities, attitudes that has a favourable effect on the advancement of core capacities.

Again, Abiodun (2019) opined that entrepreneurship education has the capability to equip any graduate with appropriate skills, knowledge, and competence, which is necessary to incorporate unemployed youths into self-reliance and employment through small scale trading and the establishment of other businesses.

Furthermore, Turner and Gianiodis (2018) argued that lucrative and lasting business creation is possible only via entrepreneurship education which provides essential abilities, skills, motivation and awareness. Eneji (2014) observed that entrepreneurship education is that process in which the learning and training activities involve pragmatic analysis of the occupational needs of students and assist them in acquiring occupational knowledge, innate abilities and skills.

Matlay (2018) suggested that comprehensive and collective strategies be utilized by the relevant authorities and stallholders to make sure that learners appropriately obtain entrepreneurship skills in tertiary institutions.

OBJECTIVES OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION

According to Paul (2005), the specific objectives of entrepreneurship education are:

- i. To provide meaningful education for the youths to be self-reliance and also to encourage them to drive profit and to be self-independent or self-employed.
- ii. To provide graduates with enough training that will make them to be creative and innovative in identifying new business opportunities.
- iii. To provide graduates with enough training in risk management and to make uncertainty bearing more possible and easy.
- iv. To give the young graduates training and support to establish a career in small and medium size businesses.
- v. To provide the graduates with training in skills that will enable them meet the man power needs of the society.
- vi. To stimulate industrial and economic growth of rural and less developed area.
- vii. To provide business enterprises both small and medium the opportunity of recruiting graduates who will be trained and tutored in the skills relevant to the management of small business centres.

According to Yaduma and Mshela (2007), entrepreneurship in technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) aims at producing better entrepreneurship through seeking to Forster in the students the following.

- i. Creativity, self-reliance and a capacity to respond to changes;
- ii. An understanding of how workplace operates;
- iii. A wider appreciation and understanding of the complexity of the community, business and industry enterprises;
- iv. Ability to take greater degree of responsibility for the quality of their work, and
- v. Ability to apply enquiry, reasoning, critical thinking, problem solving and analytical skills to different situations.

THE ROLE OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION IN NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT

The roles of entrepreneurship education in national development cannot be over emphasized. Solomon, Alabduljader and Ramani (2019) postulated that entrepreneurship education has taken a sharp shift from typical classroom lecture collection strategy to modern strategy that lay more emphasis or effort on nurturing competencies, improving expertise, abilities, attitudes that has a favourable effect on the advancement of core capacities. According to Qiang, Yeung and Matley (2022) entrepreneurship education is crucial to restoring stagnated economics, promoting growth and towering joblessness by offering new job opportunities.

Buttressing further, Ronstadt (2021) maintains that entrepreneurship education has been acknowledged as a pertinent aspect of the dynamics of all economics, and it is often regarded as the driving force in economic development and the creation of jobs. Turner and Gianiodis (2018) discovered that lucrative and lasting business creation is possible only via entrepreneurship education, which provides essential abilities, skills, motivation, and awareness corroborating this view, Acs, Szerb and Autio (2019) argued that entrepreneurship is the driver of national development and reduces poverty levels and the consequences of factors like culture, access to funds and modern technologies. Indeed, entrepreneurship education has also been discovered to be a factor that can spur the wanted economic transformation in various nations (Tok, 2020)

Ejeka, Oshiogwe and Sunday (2011) expressly stated the role of entrepreneurship education as follows:

- i. Identify entrepreneurial traits of the students, motivate and develop the on how to manage their own small scale businesses.
- ii. Develop the interest and attitudes of the students towards self-reliance and self-employment;
- iii. Train potential entrepreneurs to establish small enterprises that will increase the supply of goods and services and bring about improved standard of living of the people.
- iv. Create necessary awareness and motivation in students for promoting self-employment as an alternative to wage employment.
- v. Promote entrepreneurship among students/graduates so as to enable them make effective contribution to the economic development of the nation;
- vi. Identify the world of work, and make choices in consonance with their potentials and interest.
- vii. Identify the world of work and its prospect and challenges.
- viii. Choose an enterprise and a career.
- ix. Stimulate them to look for funds to go into business.
- x. Bring job satisfaction (economically, psychologically, and socially).
- xi. Discourage girls from becoming prostitutes if what they need to survive is money.
- xii. Make the individual his/her own boss and be free from job rules, regulations, routine work, external annual assessments for promotion, worries about gratuity, working place politics and the likes and dislikes of bosses.
- xiii. By extension, to the parents, it will take away economic dependence on their children.
- xiv. It will put more at their disposal to improve their standard of living.
- xv. To the business community or society in general:

- a) It reduces the level of unemployment, the number of dependent relatives, encourages healthy competition among entrepreneurs and produces a variety of products and services.
- b) It increases productivity and also reduces some social/society's vices such as kidnapping, banditry etc.
Others are:-
 - i. Provision of knowledge, skills, attitudes and motivation to students for entrepreneurial success in any facet of human endeavours.
 - ii. Equip individuals with ability to seek investment opportunities and maximize returns from those investment.
 - iii. It assists in wealth creation and decreasing unemployment, leads to creative thinking and new discoveries, and improves the overall production of a nation.

Through entrepreneurship education, people especially in higher institutions including those with disabilities learn organizational skills, including time management, leadership development and interpersonal skills all of which are highly transferable skills sought by employers (Ubogu, 2011).

According to Yaduma and Mshela (2007) entrepreneurship in Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) aims at producing better entrepreneurs through seeking to foster in the students the following.

- i. Creativity self-reliance and a capacity to respond to changes;
- ii. An understanding of how workplace operates;
- iii. A wider appreciation and understanding of the complexity of the community, business and industry enterprises;
- iv. Ability to take greater degree of responsibility for the quality of their work, and
- v. Ability to apply enquiry, reasoning critical thinking, problem solving and analytical skills to different situations.

b) ***Vocational Education***

Makpju (2003) views vocational education as education that is designed to equip the individual for entry into profession associated with the use and application of basic principles of science and technology apparatus and machinery in the creation of goods and services and finding answers to societal problems for survival.

Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014) defined vocational and technical education as a comprehensive term referring to those aspects of educational process involving in addition to general education the study of technologies as and related science and acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding and knowledge relating to occupations in various sectors of the economic and social life.

Okoro (1993) in Ojimba (2012) described vocational education as any form of education whose primary purpose is to prepare persons for employment in recognized occupation. Ben (2011) also posits that vocational education is a training which leads to any occupation, career or profession that requires specialized manipulative training that will culminate at attitudinal change in the learners. To Ibanga (2017) vocational education is a kind of training which leads to the acquisition of knowledge, competencies, structural activities acquired during formal, on-the-job and off-the-job training that provides the trainee with the opportunity of employment in different industries and the capability of being self-employed.

Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004) in Morebise (2022) emphasized that the concept of vocational education to include an integrate part of general education, a means of preparing for participation in world of work, an aspect of lifelong learning and a preparation for responsible citizenship and an instrument for promoting environmentally health sustainable development.

Vocational education performs very crucial role in the enhancement of human development in any nation by equipping individuals with functional skills for employment, promoting entrepreneurship and driving socio-economic growth. Suffice it to say that individuals who undergo vocational training can use their newly acquired knowledge across various fields and sectors. According to Rao, Nagaraj, Ansari and Tripathy (2024), equipping people with the knowledge and skills acquired for different jobs and industries is the main impetus of vocational education, providing people with practical skills and hands on training, they increase employment, particularly in sectors such as manufacturing, construction, health care, hospitality and information technology. He explained that vocational education fostered entrepreneurial skills, which not only equips individuals for jobs but also nurtures a spirit of entrepreneurship. Vocational training programmes provide aspiring entrepreneurs the knowledge and tools, they need to maintain and start their own businesses. He further argued that vocational training programmes also provide the following: Industry relevance and innovation, closing the skills gap, co-operation between industry and academia, inclusive development, meeting global standards, promotion of lifelong learning supporting sustainable development and women's empowerment.

The broad objectives vocational and technical education as contained in the National Policy on Education (2004) are to provide trained manpower in business particularly at craft, advance craft and technical levels, applied sciences, technology and provide technical knowledge and vocational skills necessary for industrial commercial, agricultural and economic development. Other objectives are to give training in necessary skills that can lead to the production of technicians, craftsmen and other skilled personnel who will be innovative and self-dependent, give an introduction to professional studies in engineering and other technologies and enable our young men and women to have a smart understanding of the increasing sophistication of technology.

Other aims and objectives of vocational and technical education as advocated by Morebise (2022) are as follows:

- i. Meet education demands of the population, support professionalism, career development and social protection of individuals.
- ii. Feed economy with qualified staff competitive both local and international labour market and to ensure a match between the fast changing labour market and vocational and technical education system.
- iii. Maintain competitiveness of employed be retraining professional development.
- iv. Foster appropriation of the people's educational capacities with the new socio-economic conditions to support self-employment and entrepreneurship.
- v. Support student mobility.
- vi. Ensure professional development of minority groups and create employment opportunities for them.
- vii. Develop lifelong learning.
- viii. Develop school business partnership in vocational and technical education.

Vocational education is also aimed at improving the independence of individuals in entrepreneurship, according to the competencies they have (Kiennedy, 2011). To Carr and Hartnelt (2002) in Setiyawami (2019) the paradigm of vocational education is economic, to contribute to the regeneration and modernization of industries and so advance the economic development and growth of modern society.

Again, Wilkin's (2001) in Setiyamami (2019) states that vocational education is one of the key factors in ensuring economic development, competitiveness and social stability in all countries, both developing and industrialized.

Asogwa and Diogwu (2007) also argued that there is an urgent need for Nigeria's attention to be redirected towards self-reliant and sustainable means of live hood which vocational and technical education provide.

OBJECTIVES OF VOCATIONAL EDUCATION

The objectives of vocational education as identified by the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004) in its National Policy on Education are:-

- i. To provide trained man power in applied sciences, technology and business particularly at craft, advanced craft and technical level.
- ii. To provide the technical knowledge and vocational skills necessary for agricultural, commerce and economic development, and
- iii. To give training and impart necessary skills to individuals who shall be self-reliance economically. Both the objectives of entrepreneurship and vocational education are directed towards training of students for self-reliance.

c) *Graduates Unemployability*

Unemployment has been described as a situation where people who are willing and capable of working are unable to find suitable paid employment. According to Omitogun and Lange (2017) unemployment is a situation whereby people who are physically fit, capable, qualified and ready to work at any time are without jobs.

The author of this write-up is of the opinion that un-employment is a condition in which people who are economically active and are prepared to work but without work and this including those who have lost their job and those who voluntarily left work. Unemployment has constituted some socio-economic challenges to the society. According to Shadare and Elegbede (2012) in Onoyase (2019) unemployment is the greatest challenges confronting the labour market and every economy of the countries concerned regardless of the level of development or civilization. In the same vein, Muhammadu, Oye and Inuwa (2011) argued that unemployment posed a series of serious development problems and is increasingly more serious all over Nigeria.

In researches conducted by Sara (2008) and Taudama (2009) it was discovered that some years back graduates of tertiary institutions easily got employed after graduation from schools but the situation has drastically become difficult as the number of graduates continue to soar, coupled with the shortage of vacancies.

Again, Naong (2011) Maintained that many of the graduates in South-Africa often battle to get employment because of the wrong field of study chosen by them.

Also Safyau and Alimburza (2011) in Sara and Mburza (2011) argued that one of the reasons why graduates find it difficult to secure jobs after graduation can be traced to

inadequate curricula adopted by their institutions. They further emphasized that graduates do not have appropriate job competencies required by their employers.

ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND VOCATIONAL EDUCATION AS A PANACEA FOR UNEMPLOYMENT IN NIGERIA

The issue of entrepreneurship and vocational education is a very crucial remedy for poverty and unemployment in Nigeria. It is a kind of education that prepares an individual for lifelong learning process by which he/she is armed mentally and physically with entrepreneurial skills for effective delivery thereby empowering him/her to contribute to environmentally sound and sustainable development through his participation in other areas of his life.

From the above, it can be seen that the knowledge acquired through entrepreneurship education if properly harmonized can solve the problems of unemployment that is too rampant in our society today. Some of the ways are presented below:

- i. Entrepreneurship education can enable one to make judicious use of resources for the upliftment of himself from the scourges of unemployment.
- ii. The experiences or skills acquired from entrepreneurship education can enable the learner to develop the insight needed to discover and create entrepreneurial opportunities and also the expertise to successfully start and manage their own business.
- iii. Through the knowledge acquired from entrepreneurship education one is provided with the right skills to be gainfully employed in either self-employment or paid employment.
- iv. With the knowledge of entrepreneurship education, one can always use it to tap and make use of locally produced materials within his environment.

People who are exposed to entrepreneurship education have more opportunities to exercise creative freedom, higher self-esteem and over all greater sense of control over their own lives.

Ashmore (1990) posits that vocational education has always been dedicated to preparing its graduates for employment in the work place. The students learn job specific and employability skills and are given opportunities to use these skills through work experience programmes that connect with the business community. These experiences help students from a base of knowledge about the function and operation of a business and develop some level of similarity and comfort with the business environment.

The writer is to the opinion that entrepreneurship and vocational education properly implemented in our educational system can lead to self-reliance.

PROBLEMS MILITATING AGAINST THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND VOCATIONAL EDUCATION IN NIGERIA

Despite the laudable objectives of entrepreneurship and vocational education, there are problems militating against its development. Some of these problems are:

- i. Inadequate supply of equipment and instructional materials for the teaching and learning of this form of education affect its development because practically oriented courses cannot be taught without the right equipment, Ehiamentor (1990) states that:

The lack of teaching materials makes teaching difficult and learning an impossible task. For effective teaching and learning to take place all the needed equipment and materials have to be provided.

- ii. Insufficient funding: The Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004) emphasized that it has noted that education is an expensive social services which requires adequate financial provision from all tiers of government for successful implementation of functional educational programmes. In spite of the pious objectives of entrepreneurship and vocational education, the fund allocation for educational programmes have been grossly inadequate. In fact, it is a known fact that finance is the major constraint in educational development.
- iii. Lack of qualified teachers in vocational education areas. One of the greatest problems facing education generally in Nigeria is lack of qualified teachers especially in the areas of vocational education and the mass exodus of teachers to other lucrative areas of the economy.
- iv. Shortage of relevant textbooks, journals and magazines. Inadequacies of relevant textbooks on the various vocational education subject areas are causing serious handicap to students and the teachers alike.
- v. Lack of political will be the government in promoting entrepreneurship and vocational education is another problem that affects its development. These problems and others affect the development of this desirous programme (entrepreneurship and vocational education).

CONCLUSION

No nation whether developed or developing can achieve its employment goals without focusing on entrepreneurship and vocational education entrepreneurship and vocational education is increasingly becoming very important because the world is confronted with enormous challenges that extend well beyond the global economy.

In order to curb unemployment and poverty problem in the society, the country is in need of more entrepreneurial societies who could address this fact changing problem. The society needs innovators and entrepreneurs who can not only create jobs and value but also empower others to dream of a better future.

SUGGESTION/RECOMMENDATION

Below are some of the recommendations on how entrepreneurship and vocational education can be made functional for self-reliance.

- i. Modern and qualitative equipment for the teaching of practically oriented courses for the acquisition of the needed skill should be provided for more oriented result or output.
- ii. The government should give priority to the funding of education in general and specifically vocational education programmes and more focus should be on skills acquisition for self-reliance, so that the rate of unemployment and the heavy reliance on white collar jobs can be reduced to the barest minimum.
- iii. The government should embark on training of more vocational education teachers. This could be done through in-service training within and outside the country and also by awarding scholarship allowances to teachers who are interested in furthering their education in vocational education areas.
- iv. Relevant textbooks, journals and magazines should be made available for the instructors and the learners by the government and other philanthropists at subsidized rate.

- v. The government should promote the proper implementation of functional entrepreneurship and vocational education in the curriculum at all levels of education for skills acquisition.
- vi. The government should assist the graduates of vocational education to provide capital (money, equipment and tools) with which to start their own business. This could be done through National Directorate for Employment.

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